

Urban explorations for language learning: a gamified approach to teaching Italian in a university context

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Abstract

Language learning increasingly takes place beyond the language classroom in learners' own environments. Alongside this the recent technological developments and widespread use of mobile technologies challenge traditional knowledge and skills. The paper presents the *ImparApp* study that focuses on a pervasive and gamified approach to language teaching and learning. The study, conducted at Coventry University in Coventry, UK between Spring and Autumn 2016 terms, investigated language learning with mobile devices as an approach to augmenting language learning by taking learning outside the classroom into the real-world context.

This paper reports on the design, development and testing of an introductory Italian Language Learning game, i.e. *ImparApp*, that was developed with the use of MIT's TaleBlazer authoring tool. Key findings of the pilot of the game prototype are presented in this paper drawing on data collected through participant observation of the play-test phase of the study, followed by a focus groups with students (N=7), as well as through a blind-test phase of the game. Essentially the paper contributes to the field of mobile-assisted language learning with insights on pervasive and gamified approaches to teaching and learning a foreign language.

Keywords: Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL), Pervasive Learning, Game-Based Learning, Higher Education, Italian

1. Introduction

Most people now have technology that can help them learn when and wherever they choose. In fact, learners can engage in activities that are not dependent on fixed locations or devices hence they relate more closely to their immediate environments. Rightly Kukulska-Hulme (2013) claims that mobile devices provide opportunities for exploring connections between life - "what learners happen to come across" (p.2) and learning. Such developments bring great potential for innovations in teaching and learning, and inevitably also have an influence on language learning, resulting in some researchers arguing for the need to rethink practices that are related to teaching and learning of a second or foreign language.

The main aim of this paper is to present a project that focuses on a pervasive and game-based approach to teaching and learning Italian in a university context. The project involves the development of *ImparApp*, a prototype mobile game for learners of Italian Language. It utilises opportunities offered by mobile learning, and focuses in particular on the blend of activities traditionally taking place in the classroom with opportunities provided by the technology and the built environment of a city. This paper further aims to prompt considerations whether mobile learning is likely to change how languages are taught and learnt in a higher education institution.

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2. Context

2.1. Language Learning at Coventry University

Students at Coventry University can learn a foreign language by attending an Add+vantage module. These modules are credit bearing (10 credits), and aim to develop and expand students' employability skills. The participants of the study presented in this paper were attending an Italian Language Add+vantage module.

2.2 ImparApp mobile game app

The ImparApp prototype game was developed with Tale Blazer (<http://taleblazer.org/>). TaleBlazer was developed by MIT as an open-source authoring tool for pervasive gaming to allow users to develop location-based augmented reality games (see Fig. 1).

The ImparApp game engages learners in a range of experiences and interactions as they move around their real physical location seeking to solve a time travel mystery. Specific tasks are triggered by learners' Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates, which prompt the users to explore the city by providing information about Coventry's history and built heritage. These tasks focus on the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing. Importantly, the app allows the learners and tutors to monitor progress via a leaderboard. The design of the app is discussed in detail in Morini et al. (2016), where it is noted that a key aspect of the design approach is that it allows its users to experience their everyday living contexts and their course's content in a new and playful way.

Figure 1: Screenshots of the ImparApp prototype game

2.2.1 Content and Learning Objectives

The content and learning objectives of the ImparApp prototype game are well aligned to the curriculum of Absolute Beginners Italian Course at Coventry University (A130DEL), as in its final version ImparApp aspires to be integrated in an eleven-week Absolute Beginners' Module in Italian at the university. The level of linguistic competence covered in the ImparApp is equivalent to that of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages level A1: Breakthrough (half).

The ImparApp is designed to be used in a blended mode: learners spend one week in the classroom with a tutor, and the following week completing challenges and tasks with the app in self-guided mode. Through the targeted use of this app in a beginners module a student will have opportunities to practice speaking and write short passages using appropriate grammatical structures for the task and the level. Further to

this, a student should be in a position to recognise information and understand short texts with simple familiar words and phrases about themselves, their family, and concrete situations they know well.

In its current form the ImparApp prototype game consists of four parts. Aspects of the language-in-focus are introduced gradually to the user. To explain: text in Part 1 is in English (see Fig. 1) while Part 2 makes use of English and includes translation in Italian in brackets (see Fig. 1). Part 3 is in Italian and includes translation in English in brackets and finally Part 4 is only in Italian. The four parts cover the following topics: yourself and others; work and family; routines, free time, leisure activities; food and drinks. The app also embeds content that aims at raising students awareness of the Italian culture.

3. Method

The development of the ImparApp aims to investigate the crossings of game-based learning and pervasive learning in support of language teaching and learning and further to empirically evaluate the consistency of a holistic and modular design model as a tool to guide the design process, as suggested by Arnab et al. (2015) (see Fig.2).

Layer 4: Technology	Interfaces	Media	Analytics	Communication	Storage
Layer 3: Gameful Design	Mechanics	Dynamics	Aesthetics	EX	UX
Layer 2: Learning Dynamics	Mode	Location	Activities	Assessment	
Layer 1: Learning Context	Learners	Pedagogy	Learning units	KPI	In/non/ formal

Figure 2: Holistic and modular approach (Arnab et al., 2015)

Drawing on this model, the research team designed a pilot study to inform the research and development of the ImparApp. The pilot study took place in Spring and Summer Terms 2016 and are described in the sections that follow.

3.1 Play -Test session

3.1.1 Participants

The play-test session involved testing of Part 1 of the game. The participants were seven students (N=7) attending a Lower Intermediate level Italian Language module at Coventry University. The students were selected as their advanced knowledge of the Italian language was seen as allowing them to focus on usability and engagement aspects of the game (Layer 2/Layer 3 in Fig. 2). Members of the research team accompanied the students, who were split in three groups (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Play-Test session in the city of Coventry

3.1.2 Data

Data was collected through a number of open-ended questions posed to the participants at the beginning and at the end of the play-test session; participant observation conducted by members of the research team using a structured observation sheet throughout the session; and a focus group with participants, tutors and researchers that took place right after the session.

3.1.3 Findings and discussion

The analysis of the data points to findings relevant to language learning. Despite the overwhelmingly positive reaction to the app, observations from the Play-Test sessions show that students had limited interactions in the language-in-focus. This is seen as being associated with the design of tasks in Part 1 (i.e. introduction of the game, learning Italian phonetics and pronunciation), hence further iterations of the app will allow for more interactions among the users and with their built environment. It is further noted that most discussions the participants had were related to finding their orientation, which was clearly viewed as a key aspect of the game experience. Indications of incidental learning also emerge in the data. For example a participant referred to a historic pub in Coventry: “Whitefriars Pub... I didn’t know anything about the pub and the little alley behind the cathedral”.

In addition to this, in the focus group discussion that followed the play-test session students suggested for audio in Italian (see Fig. 1) and Italian music to be embedded in the app. As already discussed in Morini et al. (2016) feedback received by students (e.g. zoom map, avatar creation, videos) informed development of the four parts of the app. During this process the team also responded to students’ concerns related to the use of English and language-in-focus by adding a gradual introduction of the language-in-focus in the game’s descriptions and instructions (see section 2.2.1, Fig. 1).

Finally in the focus group discussion participants touched upon issues of assessment. Students shared some concerns and expressed preference to traditional methods of assessment. For example a participant said “you can go off the app and do the assessment...checking answers on a laptop. So, still you [teachers] need to do assessment in the class”.

3.2 Blind-Test session

The blind-test session kicked-off in June 2016 with a general invitation (via Student Union, Facebook, email lists, posters across campus) to students at Coventry University (Fig. 4). It will be completed during the induction week at the beginning of the academic year 2016-17, when the research team aims to target

new students and capitalise emergent benefits of the game such as familiarisation with the city centre as well as the social components that were observed during the Play-Test session.

3.2.1 Data

Data is collected through a number of open-ended questions included on a Google Form that a user is prompted to fill-in while playing the game. To date data collection is still on-going and is expected to be completed in Autumn 2016.

Figure 4: Invitation to the blind-test session

4. Conclusions

The paper presented a project currently developed at Coventry University, which examines new possibilities that emerge in language learning and teaching when pervasive approaches to learning are combined with game-based techniques. It was shown that ImparApp game allows its users to experience their everyday living contexts and their course's content in a new and playful way. As a result the paper prompts us to rethink the design and organisation of a university language course in terms of learner's experience, with an emphasis on context, learner's movement and interactions of the physical and virtual worlds that the learners find themselves in.

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